

CLASSIFICATION OF TYPES OF THE HISTORY OF THE ORIGIN OF SCULPTURE

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Abstract: This article provides information about the history of the origin, etymology, distribution and types of sculptural art.

Key words: sculpture, animalistics, landscape, still life, monumental sculpture, decorative sculpture, bench sculpture.

Sculpture is a type of fine art. This type of art is based on the three-dimensional representation of existence in volumetric forms. The object of the image is mainly a person; as well as animals (animalistics), nature (landscape) and objects (still life). The 2 main types of sculpture are the round sculpture that allows you to look around and the embossed (bubble) image that can be seen only from one side. The relief, in turn, is divided into bas-relief, which is slightly raised in relation to the surface, and high relief, in which the image is greatly raised in relation to the surface. There is also a more engraved look, where the image is worked on a flat surface due to the play of light.

Sculpture is divided into several types according to its function and content. These are:

- Monumental sculpture;
- Decorative sculpture;
- Bench sculpture.

Types of small sculptures develop in close contact with each other and have their own characteristics. Monumental sculpture related to the art of architecture includes monuments, memorials, sculptural ensembles erected in order to perpetuate the memory of important historical events, famous people, they express great content

and have independent importance; however, this type of sculpture should be in harmony with the immediate environment, architectural structures and nature, which will give it more grandeur and impressiveness.

One of the characteristic features of monumental sculpture is the depiction of heroes in an upbeat spirit. Since monumental sculptures are intended to be seen from afar, large solid forms are widely used; small elements of a person's face, folds in clothes, small parts may not be shown.

Decorative sculpture includes various decorative sculptures used to decorate parks, avenues, streets and gardens, as well as the walls of architectural buildings; Symbolic images and animal forms are widely used in his works.

Embossed images on the walls of buildings, decorations on the surface of practical art objects, fountains, fences, and artistic gates are also examples of this sculpture.

Easel sculpture includes works that have an independent content and are not subject to other types of art; they are intended to be placed in exhibitions, museum rooms and interior of houses. In this type of works, reality is reflected in its entirety, and there is a great opportunity to reveal subtle changes in the human psyche, his inner experiences, and his mood. Easel sculptural works are bust (portrait to the waist), torso, statue (life-size representation of the human body), figurine (statues smaller than life size), colossus (oversized statues, for example, the Colossus of Rhodes), genre sculpture (in a certain environment the person or group of people depicted) and in another form. Small-scale sculpture is close to practical decorative art in its character. This includes tabletop sculptures made of ceramic, porcelain, and other raw materials. One of the most common types is terracotta; the art of making medals and glyptics also belong to this type.

In sculpture, the artist increases the impact of the work by using the play of light and shadow (the sculpture comes alive when the light falls, and the light-shadow interaction changes in it, as a result, the viewer's impression of it changes). This is especially useful for monumental and decorative sculptures, because the

morning sunlight gives a different charm to a sculpture placed in a square or boulevard, while the evening sun's rays add a different charm. Sculptures do not end with the reflection of a person's appearance, quiet or active state, experiences, excitement, sadness, etc. are expressed in the work.

Sculptor's skills, correctly found movements, facial expressions play an important role in making the work effective. Various materials such as stone, granite, bronze, marble, wood, metal (precious metals such as gold, silver, pickel), cement, plaster are used for sculptural works. The raw material chosen in sculpture determines its color. There are cases of painting statues only in folk sculpture. When creating sculptural works, soft materials (special clay, wax, plasticine, etc.), hard materials (different types of stones, wood, etc.) are created by cutting (burning) or removing unnecessary parts by carving; materials that have the property of transitioning from a liquid state to a solid state (various metals, plaster, concrete, etc.) are cast using a mold; special types of clay are used in the preparation of ceramic sculptural works, the form is covered with a painted pattern or colored glaze and fired in special furnaces. The sculptural work is placed on a base (pedestal or pedestal); sometimes, the sculptor can use sculptures and reliefs mounted on several bases to reveal his goal.

Sculpture has been formed since time immemorial - in primitive society with the emergence of human labor and religious concepts, and in the process of making it, it began to depict one's feelings and experiences with the style of sculpture (grinding, processing, making shapes from soft clay). Round, cave or stone relief sculptures of animals are an expression of the views of primitive people. Embossed images were made on the surface of soft stone, bone and wood, were used to decorate work and hunting tools, and also as amulets. Great success was achieved in the production of practical art objects with embossed images from gold and other precious materials, and clay figurines (Scythian culture, ceramic figurines from Nok on the African continent, etc.).

From the era of slavery, a new stage in sculpture began, which is distinguished by the diversity of styles, the scope of themes and types. In this respect, the Ancient East has a special place in sculpture: for the first time, majestic statues, easel portraits, lively, action-filled relief images were created. Monuments of Sumer and Akkad, Babylon and Assyria, majestic statues in Egypt, elegant reliefs are rare monuments of this period. The magnificent sculptures and bas-reliefs of Khorezm, Sughd, Bactrian monuments, Tuproqkala, Varakhsha, Afrosiyob, Kholchayon, Dalvarzintepa, Kuva created in the Middle East, including the territory of Uzbekistan, small figurines, and various artistic forms used in the decoration of practical art objects testify to the rich culture of the period.

In ancient times, relief and portrait reached a higher stage of development, great progress was made in expressing the mental state of a person. In the sculptures created in Greece and partly in ancient Rome, human feelings and its perfection took the leading place, truthfulness prevailed in the depiction, creating a physically strong and spiritually beautiful human image was the main goal of Greek sculpture (Phidias and Myron, Polycletus and Praxiteles). Roman sculptors made great achievements in the art of portraiture, in their works complex human experiences were depicted in strong realism, the physical and spiritual state of a person was openly shown; A statue of a cavalry commander was created for the first time in Rome, great achievements were also made in the relief image: columns and triumphal crowns dedicated to important historical events were decorated with realistic relief images.

In the countries of the middle Ages, sculpture did not develop uniformly everywhere. In the countries of South and South-East Asia (India, Indonesia and Indochina) majestic and exquisite monuments were created, while in the countries of the Middle and Middle East, the practical decorative art of sculpture is mixed with stone carving, wood and stone carving, jewelry and carvings. Found its expression, was widely used in the manufacture of household items, jewelry, and decoration of buildings. In European countries, the Christian religion was the main force for the development of sculpture: sculpture workshops were established under the

cathedrals, where future sculptors were prepared, round sculptures and reliefs were created for temples, which served to promote religious ideas.

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